

Superparamagnetism and ferrimagnetism in the $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ nanoscale powder

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Abstract

Using combined synthesis modes and optimized conditions for ultrasonic dispersion, we obtained a single-phase nanosized $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ powder having a high degree of superstructural ordering of Fe and Mo cations (88%) and an average grain size of 70.8 nm. The results of the Mössbauer spectroscopy and magnetic measurements show that the obtained nanosized strontium ferromolybdate powder is in a magnetically inhomogeneous state, consisting of superparamagnetic and ferrimagnetic phases. In comparison with the superparamagnetic component of magnetization, the ferrimagnetic component has higher values and rises smoothly until reaching saturation as the temperature decreases. Showing that there is no exchange magnetic interaction between the grains in the superparamagnetic phase, allowed us to estimate the critical sizes, of nanoparticles, d_{spm} , in the single-domain state using the Néel-Brown model. The obtained value of d_{spm} is smaller than the size of the single-domain particles, which confirms the absence of the frozen state in some of the superparamagnetic particles. These results are important for understanding the effects of nanosized grains on the magnetic properties and features of magnetization of the $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ polydisperse powder, a promising material for spintronic device applications.

Keywords: Perovskites, Sol-gel processes, Atomic force microscopy, Magnetic properties

1. Introduction

Nanoscale magnetic structures are widely used in modern applications, such as ultrahigh-density magnetic recording systems, various magnetic field sensors, spin transistors, magnetic fluids for magnetic resonance imaging, magnetic hyperthermia, and others [1]. Differences between the physico-chemical properties of nanomaterials, and those of bulk materials of the same chemical composition, are due to the greater influence of the increased surface, various kinds of defects and inhomogeneities. Structural inhomogeneities cause an uneven distribution of magnetization with formation of a stochastic magnetic structure, while maintaining the effective ferrimagnetic order within the distances exceeding the grain size [2].

A class of promising materials for spintronics is represented by nanosized semimetallic ferrimagnets $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ which have an ordered double perovskite structure, which attract particular interest due to their significant magnetoresistance of $\sim 38\%$ in relatively weak magnetic fields ($B = 1$ T at $T = 50$ K), large values of the Curie temperature ($T_C = 400 - 450$ K) and practically 100% degree of spin polarization [3-7]. These unique magnetic properties are quite important for practical applications [8-10].

In the industrial use of magnets, improving the technology of obtaining structurally perfect $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ samples with reproducible optimum magnetic properties remains a significant problem. Spin polarization can exist under certain conditions, one of which is the presence in the planes perpendicular to the crystallographic axis c , of a superstructural ordering of Fe and Mo cations located in the centers of octahedra with oxygen anions O1 and O2 at the vertices. The presence of various zero-dimensional defects, especially anti-structural ones ($[\text{Mo}]_{\text{Fe}}$, $[\text{Fe}]_{\text{Mo}}$), and anionic vacancies V_0 , causes distortion of the real crystal structure, leading to redistribution of the electron density and formation of Fe^{2+} ($3d^6$, $S = 2$) and Mo^{6+} ($4d^0$, $S = 0$) cations. Diamagnetic cations Mo^{6+} ($4d^0$) do not participate in the exchange interactions, and only negative exchange interactions are possible between Fe^{2+} ($3d^6$) or Fe^{3+} ($3d^5$) ions, which leads to formation of the antiferromagnetic ordering of their magnetic moments. Therefore, the distortion of the crystal lattice caused by cationic and anionic defects has a strong impact on the magnetic and electric properties of the double perovskite [6, 9, 11-15].

To purposefully optimize the production of a magnet with specific magnetic properties, it is important to establish a relationship between the macroscopic and microscopic parameters of the material: the saturation magnetization, coercive force, and the overall shape of the temperature and field dependence are determined by the exchange interaction constant A , the magnetic anisotropy field H_a , local magnetic anisotropy constant K , spin-wave stiffness D , and grain size d . In calculating these key parameters, determining the applied properties of a nanoscale magnet, the main point is the assumption that the easy magnetization axes in $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ grains are randomly oriented. In

addition, in the ensemble of polydisperse nanoparticles, there is a scatter in the size near their single-domain structure and the critical radius of the superparamagnetic state, which affects the controllability and reproducibility of their properties. Although the magnetic properties of $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ nanoparticles have been widely studied, it remains unclear how the nanoscale nature of the grains affects, among others, the saturation magnetization, magnetic anisotropy energy, spin stiffness coefficient, and critical sizes of particles in the superparamagnetic state. Here we study these effects.

2. Material and methods

$\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (99.5 %), $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (99.5 %), $(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24}$ (99.9 %) and high purity grade citric acid monohydrate $\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_7 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (99.9 %) from Sigma-Aldrich were used as starting reagents for the synthesis of the nanosized $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ compound by the citrate-gel technique. To obtain a colloidal solution, aqueous solutions of $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were mixed at a molar ratio: $2\text{Sr}:\text{Fe} = 2:1$. Citric acid was added to the solution at a molar ratio: 6.5 (citric acid): $\text{Fe} = 6.5:1$. The aqueous solution of $(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24}$ was added to the solution with strontium and iron nitrates at a molar ratio $\text{Mo}:\text{Fe} = 1:1$. With constant stirring ethylenediamine (EDA) was added until the pH of the solution became equal to 4, then the solution was evaporated on the magnetic stirrer at a temperature of 352 K. The resulting substance was placed in an oven at 370 K, heated at a rate of 0.4 deg/min to 470 K, held at this temperature for 18 hours, and then cooled in the switched-off thermosetting mode. The obtained solid foam was crushed and annealed at $T=770\text{K}$ and $p\text{O}_2 = 0.21 \times 10^5$ Pa for 10 hours. The obtained powder was annealed in a flow of 5% H_2/Ar gas mixture at 1170 K for 5 hours and quenched at room temperature [11-12].

The phase composition and lattice parameters were examined using the X-ray diffraction (XRD) with the DRON-3 diffractometer in $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation at room temperature at a rate of $60^\circ/\text{h}$ for angles $\Theta = 10\text{--}90^\circ$. The structural refinement was performed using the Rietveld analysis with the ICSD – PDF2 database (Release 2000) and PowderCell and FullProf software for all samples. The degree of superstructural ordering P of iron and molybdenum cations was calculated using the formula $P = (2 \cdot \text{SOF} - 1) \times 100\%$, where SOF is the position occupancy factor. The concentration of antistructural defects n was calculated using the formula $n = (100\% - P)/2$.

The grain sizes were estimated using atomic force microscopy (NT-206 AFM). The particle size distribution was obtained using the dynamic light scattering (DLS) analysis on a Zetasizer Nano ZS90 nanoparticles analyzer (Malvern Panalytical, UK).

The Mössbauer spectra were measured using MS1104Em spectrometer with ^{57}Co in the Rh matrix as a source of γ -quanta, in the mode of constant accelerations in the geometry of a moving source; the velocity varied according to the triangle law. For cooling, the samples were placed in the

CCS-850 refrigerated helium cryostat (Janis Inc); heating of the samples was performed in a furnace in air. A model interpretation of the spectra was carried out using SpectrRelax software [16]. The isomeric shifts were calculated relative to metallic α -Fe.

The magnetic properties of the samples were studied in the temperature range from 4.2 to 300 K in a magnetic field of (0-10 T) in a universal liquid helium-free high field measurement system (Cryogenic Ltd.).

3. Results and Discussion

Using the citrate-gel technique, we obtained a single-phase $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ compound having the crystal lattice parameters $a = b = 5.56 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 7.89 \text{ \AA}$, $V=244.27 \text{ \AA}^3$, with $P=88 \%$ and $n=6 \%$ (see Fig. 1) [11, 12, 15].

Agglomerations were observed in the $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ nanopowder (Fig. 1, inset), therefore ultrasonic dispersion was used to obtain highly dispersed particles with an average size $d_{av} < 100 \text{ nm}$. In a suspension of the composition of 25 ml ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$) + 0.01 g ($\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$) + 0.05 g (Tween 20), subjected to the ultrasonic dispersion for 60 minutes, the sizes of agglomerates gradually decreased from 230 nm and the size of grains reached 70.8 nm.

To establish the size distribution of particles, the DLS analysis was carried out (Fig. 2). The best approximation of the size distribution with the smallest dispersion and the establishment of the average size of particles can be achieved using the log-normal distribution:

$$(d) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}d\sigma} \exp\left\{-\frac{[\ln d - \ln d_{av}]^2}{2\sigma}\right\}, \quad (1)$$

here d_{av} and σ are the average diameter of a particle and dispersion of the particle size distribution, respectively [17]. According to the log-normal distribution data for the nanosized powder subjected to ultrasonic dispersion for 60 minutes, the calculated average particle diameter $d_{av} = 70.8 \text{ nm}$. In this case, the dispersion of the size distribution σ of the $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ particles is 0.243 nm, and the coefficient of determination when approximated by a log-normalized function is $R^2 = 0.997$, which indicates a close fit (Fig.2).

The temperature dependences of the magnetization $M(T)$ were obtained in the “zero-field cooling” (ZFC) and “field-cooling” (FC) modes (Fig. 3). When a magnetic field with an induction $B = 0.01 \text{ T}$ is turned on at $T = 4.2 \text{ K}$, followed by heating, a sharp increase in the magnetization of the powder occurs in the ZFC dependences up to the critical point temperature T_B , which delimits areas with different magnetic states [18]. With a further increase in temperature, a smooth decrease in the magnetization is observed. The curves of the ZFC and FC dependences converge at the irreversibility temperature $T_H = 164 \text{ K}$, at which ferrimagnetic particles of a maximal size unfreeze.

We can assume that at $T < T_B$ the nanoparticles are in a metastable superparamagnetic state and a frozen ferrimagnetic state. The presence of superparamagnetism at $T > T_B$, where T_B is the blocking temperature, leads to a magnetically ordered state in which the resulting magnetic moment of a single-domain particle is influenced by thermal fluctuations [19-21].

Because the relaxation time τ_{sp} of superparamagnetic particles is small, measuring methods with $\tau_{meas} \sim \tau_{sp}$ are needed to study their true magnetic state. In the Mössbauer spectroscopy, the characteristic measurement time is determined by the time of the Larmor precession of the iron nucleus, $\tau_{meas} = 2.5 \times 10^{-8}$ s [22]. For example, the Mössbauer spectroscopy has been used to study the change in the superparamagnetic contribution to magnetization with an increase in the size of the Fe_2O_3 nanoparticles from 25 to 69 nm [23, 24].

The presence of a two-phase magnetic state is indicated by the Mössbauer spectroscopy data. We found that the Mössbauer spectrum measured at 10 K is well approximated by four Zeeman sextets, which indicates the presence of both ordered and disordered regions with respect to Fe and Mo cations, as well as the presence of iron cations in the state of mixed valence ($Fe^{2+/3+}$). An increase in the temperature above $T_B = 20$ K leads to a superposition of sextets and a quadrupole doublet. The doublet refers to the paramagnetic state of the Fe ions in superparamagnetic grains of $Sr_2FeMoO_{6-\delta}$. Moreover, as the temperature rises, the area occupied by the doublet increases, reaching its maximum size at 300 K in the Mössbauer spectra (Fig. 4). This can be explained as follows: at low temperatures ($T < T_B$), a part of the $Sr_2FeMoO_{6-\delta}$ nanograins is in the metastable (blocked) superparamagnetic state. Their Mössbauer spectrum has the form of a Zeeman sextet. The other part of the nanosized grains is in the ferrimagnetic state and is also described by the sextets. The presence of several sextets indicates a mixed valence state of the iron cations due to the difference in the cationic and anionic environments of Fe. At $T > T_B$, superparamagnetic particles pass from the metastable (blocked) to the stable superparamagnetic state, their Mössbauer spectrum takes the form of a quadrupole doublet characteristic of the paramagnetic state. Thus, the temperature evolution of the Mössbauer spectra of the $Sr_2FeMoO_{6-\delta}$ polydisperse nanopowder is due to its magnetically two-phase state, in which some of the grains are in the ferrimagnetic state, whereas the others are in the superparamagnetic state.

To calculate the local magnetic anisotropy field H_{fa} and the magnetic anisotropy constant K_f for ferrimagnetic particles, the field values of the magnetization of the $Sr_2FeMoO_{6-\delta}$ nanopowder were analyzed, using the law of approach to saturation, which can be represented as [25-28]:

$$M(H) = M_{fH0} \left(1 - \frac{a}{H} - \frac{b}{H^2} \right) + M_{fH1} H, \quad (2)$$

where M_{fH0} is the saturation magnetization of ferrimagnetic particles, a and b are the constants associated with magnetic inhomogeneities and magnetocrystalline anisotropy of the samples, respectively. The coefficient M_{fH1} is associated with the spontaneous domain magnetization and is

active at high temperatures. Using eq. 2, the local magnetic anisotropy field of the ferrimagnetic particles H_{fa} was calculated according to the expression:

$$(\tilde{\alpha}H_{fa})^2 = b, \quad (3)$$

where $\tilde{\alpha}$ is the coefficient related to the symmetry of uniaxial magnetic anisotropy, $\tilde{\alpha}^2 = 1/15$ [29]. The magnetic anisotropy constant K_f of ferrimagnetic particles was calculated as:

$$K_f = H_{fa} \mu_0 M_{fH0} / 2, \quad (4)$$

where μ_0 is the magnetic permeability of the vacuum. The obtained values of the fitting coefficient M_{fH1} were low and therefore not taken into account (Fig. 5, Table 1).

The calculated values of K_f and H_{fa} differ from the results obtained previously in other works ($H_{fa}=8.7 \times 10^4$ A/m [26], $H_{fa}=1.7 \times 10^4$ A/m [30], $K_f=2.74 \times 10^4$ J/m³ [31]). This can be due to the facts that: (a) close fit according to eq. 2 did not work out ($R^2=0.9776$), and (b) the authors of the previous studies [26, 30, 31] did not separate the contributions of ferrimagnetic and superparamagnetic particles. To take into account the contribution of superparamagnetic particles to the total magnetization, we need to introduce the Langevin function into the law of approach to saturation:

$$M(H) = M_{fH0}(1 - a/H - b/H^2) + M_{SH0}(\coth(H/M_{SH1}) - M_{SH1}/H), \quad (5)$$

where M_{SH0} is the saturation magnetization of superparamagnetic particles, $M_{SH1}=k_B T / \mu_0 \mu$, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T is the temperature at which the field dependence of the magnetization was measured, and μ is the magnetic moment of the superparamagnetic particle (Fig. 5).

The local magnetic anisotropy field H_{fa} and the magnetic anisotropy constant K_f of the ferrimagnetic phase were calculated using eqs. 3 and 4, whereas the total magnetization of $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ was determined as a sum of the contributions of the ferrimagnetic and superparamagnetic phases: $M_0 = M_{fH0} + M_{SH0}$ (Table 2).

At $T < T_B$, the nanoparticles are in a metastable state in which the magnetization of the ensemble of particles exhibits a hysteresis. The T_B value can be obtained using the Néel-Brown relation for the blocking temperature:

$$T_B = KV / k_B \ln(\tau_0 / \tau) \approx KV / 25 k_B, \quad (6)$$

where V is the particle volume, K is the constant of magnetic anisotropy, which includes the bulk and surface magnetic anisotropies [32, 33]. Here, $\ln(\tau_0 / \tau_{sp}) \approx 25$, and τ_0 is the characteristic measurement time, 10^2 s in standard static magnetic measurements.

Equation (6) can be expressed for superparamagnetic particles in terms of the fitting parameters, by multiplying both its sides by TM_{SH0} :

$$25 k_B T_B T M_{SH0} = K_s V T M_{SH0}, \quad (7)$$

Considering that $k_B T = \mu_0 \mu M_{SH1}$ and $\mu = V M_{SH0}$, we obtain:

$$25 \mu_0 \mu M_{SH1} T_B M_{SH0} = \mu K_s T \rightarrow 25 \mu_0 T_B M_{SH1} M_{SH0} = K_s T \quad (8)$$

Substituting the expression for the local magnetic anisotropy field $H_{sa}=2K_s/\mu_0M_{SH0}$ into eq. 8, we obtain the formula for the local magnetic anisotropy field of a superparamagnetic particle:

$$50 \mu_0 T_B M_{SH0} M_{SH1} = H_{sa} \mu_0 M_{SH0} T \rightarrow H_{sa} = 50 T_B M_{SH1} / T \quad (9)$$

The calculated ferrimagnetic and superparamagnetic components of the field dependence of the magnetization $M(H)$ calculated using eq. 5 are shown in Fig. 6.

To estimate the critical sizes of the superparamagnetic particles, we considered the temperature dependence of the powder magnetization. As the temperature rises in the low-temperature region, the magnetic ordering is disturbed because of the excitation of magnons, with a quadratic dependence of the energy on the wave vector $E(k) \sim k^2$. The number of magnons is proportional to $T^{3/2}$, which leads to a decrease in the magnetization of $Sr_2FeMoO_{6-\delta}$ with temperature. The temperature dependence of the magnetization, according to Bloch's law, is:

$$M(T) = M_{fT0} (1 - B_T T^{3/2}), \quad (10)$$

where M_{fT0} is the maximum magnetization of the ferrimagnetic particles and B_T is the fitting coefficient corresponding to Bloch's constant. We found that the best approximation of the $M(T)$ dependence according to Bloch's law, measured in an external magnetic field of 0.01 T, was realized in the temperature range $4.2 < T < 100$ K (Fig. 7). An increase in the temperature promotes the excitation of magnons with large values of the wave vector k , which are characterized by a non-square dispersion law and interact with each other, which should be taken into account. Dyson [32] has shown that deviations from Bloch's law can be described in the model by including the term $C_T T^{5/2}$:

$$M(T) = M_{fT0} (1 - B_T T^{3/2} - C_T T^{5/2}), \quad (11)$$

where all the coefficients are positive and the third term is related to the non-square law of dispersion of the magnon spectrum. The calculated Bloch's constant $B_T = 1.15 \times 10^{-4} \text{ K}^{-3/2}$, is higher than the values of other studies (for example, $9.26 \times 10^{-5} \text{ K}^{-3/2}$ in the low-temperature range and $7.03 \times 10^{-5} \text{ K}^{-3/2}$ in the high-temperature range for $Sr_2FeMoO_{5.5}S_{0.5}$ [34]; $5.9 \times 10^{-5} \text{ K}^{-3/2}$ for $Fe_{29}Hi_{49}P_{14}B_6Si_2$ [35]). The differences in the results can be due to the fact that a close fit according to eq. 11 did not work out ($R^2 = 0.9796$).

Part of the nanopowder is in the superparamagnetic state, where the change in the magnetization is described by the Langevin function. The temperature dependence of the nanopowder magnetization is well approximated by the function:

$$M(T) = M_{fT0} (1 - B_T T^{3/2} - C_T T^{5/2}) + M_{ST0} (\coth(M_{ST1}/T) - T/M_{ST1}), \quad (12)$$

where M_{ST0} is the saturation magnetization for superparamagnetic particles; $M_{ST1} = \mu_0 \mu H / k_B$ ($R^2 = 0.9988$). According to eq. 12, the fitting parameters of the experimental temperature of magnetization measured in the FC mode are: $M_{fT0} = 27.47 \text{ A} \cdot \text{m}^2/\text{kg}$; $M_{ST0} = 23.25 \text{ A} \cdot \text{m}^2/\text{kg}$; $B_T = 4.6 \times 10^{-5} \text{ K}^{-3/2}$.

Based on the results of the approximation and taking into account the formula for a calculation of the Bloch's constant [36]:

$$B = 2.612 \frac{g\mu_B}{M_0} \left(\frac{k_B}{4\pi D} \right)^{3/2}, \quad (13)$$

where $g = 2.02$ is the Landé factor, and μ_B is the Bohr magneton, one can calculate the coefficient of the spin-wave stiffness D . The calculated value $D = 148 \text{ meV} \cdot \text{Å}^2$ is in close agreement with the results of the previous studies for $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ crystals, $D = 140\text{-}150 \text{ meV} \cdot \text{Å}^2$ at $M_{\text{sat}} = 3.3 \mu_B/\text{Fe}$ [36-38]. This result is reasonable, because the coefficient of spin-wave stiffness D is directly proportional to the exchange integral J , which in turn depends on the density of exchange interactions and, accordingly, on the concentration of antisite defects [33, 39, 40]. For the $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ crystals, the reported density of antisite defects was 5 % [38], whereas the value in this study was 6 %, indicating the accuracy of our calculations.

Using eq. 12, we calculated the temperature dependences of the magnetization $M(T)$, and its ferrimagnetic and superparamagnetic components (Fig. 8).

In comparison of the superparamagnetic component of the magnetization, the ferrimagnetic component has higher values, and rises smoothly until reaching saturation as the temperature decreases. The superparamagnetic component of the magnetization has lower values that slightly depend on temperature in the range of 300–100 K, and show a stronger dependence in the range of 100–4.2 K, which is expected.

The critical diameter d_c below which an ensemble of nanosized particles changes from a multi-domain to a single-domain structure is determined as [41]:

$$d_c = 72(AK_s)^{1/2} / \mu_0 M_{SH1}^2, \quad (14)$$

where A is the exchange interaction constant, and K_s is the constant of uniaxial magnetic anisotropy for superparamagnetic particles. The exchange interaction constant A was determined as:

$$A = \frac{k}{8\pi} \left(\frac{g\mu_B}{M_0} \right)^{-1/3} \left(\frac{2.612}{B} \right)^{2/3}. \quad (15)$$

yielding $A = 2.01 \times 10^{-12} \text{ J} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}$. For comparison, the exchange interaction constant for a ferrimagnet in which the spins are located in the lattice sites can be approximately estimated using the formula [42]:

$$A \approx (M/M_0)^2 k_B T_C / a_0,$$

where M is the magnetization at $T > 0 \text{ K}$, $M_0 = 50 \text{ A} \cdot \text{m}^2/\text{kg}$ at 0 K , and T_C is the Curie temperature.

For $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$, we define $a_0 = \sqrt[3]{a^2 c}$, where $a = 0.556 \text{ nm}$ and $c = 0.789 \text{ nm}$. Thus, $a_0 = \sqrt[3]{0.556^2 \times 0.789} = 0.625 \text{ nm} = 0.625 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}$. It was experimentally found that $M = 48 \text{ A} \cdot \text{m}^2/\text{kg}$ at $T = 25 \text{ K}$. In this case, $A \approx 8.33 \times 10^{-11} \text{ J/m}$, which does not coincide with the previous calculations, because of antisite defects in the real crystal lattice.

The critical diameter d_c of the single-domain state in $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ grains, calculated using eq. 14 is 44.5 nm, in close agreement with the results of the previous research, $d_c \sim 50$ nm [42].

To estimate the critical diameter d_{spm} of a superparamagnetic particle, we determined its volume V using eq. 7 and the expressions for the fitting coefficients:

$$V = \frac{25M_{SH1}M_{ST1}T_B k_B}{HK_S T} \quad (17)$$

Then,

$$d_{\text{spm}} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{150M_{SH1}M_{ST1}k_B T_B}{\pi HK_S T}},$$

where $T = 25$ K, $B = 0.01$ T (the conditions for measuring the field and temperature dependences of the magnetization), $T_B = 20$ K, $M_{SH1} = 1.53 \times 10^6$ A/m, $M_{ST1} = 235.37$ K. The obtained value of $d_{\text{spm}} = 24.8$ nm is smaller than the sizes of single-domain particles, which confirms the superparamagnetic state of part of these nanosized particles.

4. Conclusions

Using the citrate-gel synthesis, a single-phase nanosized $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ powder with a high degree of superstructural ordering of Fe and Mo cations ($P = 88$ %) was achieved. The optimized conditions for ultrasonic dispersion made it possible to obtain the nanopowder with an average grain size of 70.8 nm.

The results of the magnetic and Mössbauer measurements showed a two-phase magnetic structure of the nanosized $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ powder, and the dynamics of changes of its superparamagnetic and ferrimagnetic states.

We propose a new expression for the law of approach to saturation for the polydisperse magnetic two-phase state of the $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ nanopowder, which makes it possible to quantitatively describe its magnetic characteristics (the local magnetic anisotropy field and magnetic anisotropy constants) and estimate the critical size of the nanoparticles in the single-domain state.

The observed irreversibility of the temperature dependences of the magnetization (in the FC and ZFC modes) of the $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ nanopowder was explained by the presence of magnetic anisotropy and approximated for the first time taking into account the quadratic and non-quadratic dispersion laws of the magnon spectrum, and using the Langevin function. The calculated values of Bloch's coefficients, the spin-wave stiffness, and exchange interaction constant are in close agreement with the literature data.

We calculated the magnetic characteristics of the $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ nanopowders that are important for practical applications and can serve as a guideline for creating new memory elements and magnetic field sensors with improved magnetic characteristics.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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References

- [1] X.Batlle, A.Labarta, Finite size effects in fine particles: magnetic and transport properties, *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* 35 (2002) R15–R42. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0022-3727/35/6/201>
- [2] S. Blügel, T. Brückel and C. M Schneider (Eds.), *Magnetism goes Nano: Electron Correlations, Spin Transport, Molecular Magnetism*, Lecture Manuscripts of the 36th Spring School of the Institute of Solid State Research, 14-25 February 2005.
- [3] K.–I.Kobayashi, T.Kimura, H.Sawada, K.Terakura, Y.Tokura, Room–temperature magnetoresistance in an oxide material with an ordered double–perovskite structure, *Nature* 395 (1998) 677–680. <https://doi.org/10.1038/27167>.
- [4] T.–Y. Cai, S.Ju, Z.–Y.Li, Antisite disorder–induced low–field magnetoresistance in some frustrated $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_6$, *Phys.: Condens. Matter.* 18 (2006) 11347–11355. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0953-8984/18/49/025>.
- [5] D.Serrate, J.M.De Teresa, M.R.Ibarra, Double perovskites with ferromagnetism above room temperature, *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter.* 19 (2007) 023201. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0953-8984/19/2/023201>
- [6] Y.Zhang, V. Ji, K.–W. Xu, Effects of the defects on the structural, electronic and magnetic properties of $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_6$, *J. Alloys Compd.* 648 (2015) 374. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2015.06.242>
- [7] Q.Zhang, Z.F.Xu, L. F.Wang, S.H.Gao, S.J.Yuan, Structural and electromagnetic properties driven by oxygen vacancy in $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ double perovskite, *J. Alloys Compd.* 649 (2015): 1151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2015.07.211>
- [8] J.P.Zhou, R.Dass, H.Q.Yin, J.–S.Zhou, L.Rarenberg, J.B.Goodenough, Enhancement of room temperature magnetoresistance in double perovskite ferrimagnets, *J. Appl. Phys.* 87 (2000) 5037–5039. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.373240>
- [9] N.A.Kalanda, L.V.Kovalev, J.C.Waerenborgh, M.R.Soares, M.L.Zheludkevich, M.V.Yarmolich, N.A.Sobolev, Interplay of superstructural ordering and magnetic properties of the $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ double perovskite, *Science of Advanced Materials* 7 (2015) 446–454. <https://doi.org/10.1166/sam.2015.2134>
- [10] L.V.Kovalev, M.V.Yarmolich, M.L.Petrova, J.Ustarroz, H.Terryn, N.A.Kalanda, M.L.Zheludkevich, Double perovskite $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_6$ films prepared by electrophoretic deposition, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* 6 (2014) 19201–19206. <https://doi.org/10.1021/am5052125>
- [11] M.Yarmolich, N.Kalanda, S.Demyanov, H.Terryn, J.Ustarroz, M.Silibin, G.Gorokh, Influence of synthesis conditions on microstructure and phase transformations of annealed $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ nanopowders formed by citrate-gel method, *Beilstein Journal of Nanotechnology* 7 (2016) 1202–1207. <https://doi.org/10.3762/bjnano.7.111>

- [12] M.Yarmolich, N.Kalanda, S.Demyanov, Ju.Fedotova, V.Bayev, N.Sobolev, Charge ordering and magnetic properties in nanosized $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6.8}$ powders, *Phys. Status Solidi B.253* (2016) 2160–2166. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pssb.201600527>.
- [13] N.A.Liedienov, Z.Wei, V.M.Kalita, A.V.Pashchenko, Q.Li, I.V.Fesych, V.A.Turchenko, C.Hou, X.Wei, B.Liu, A.T.Kozakov, Spin-dependent magnetism and superparamagnetic contribution to the magnetocaloric effect of non-stoichiometric manganite nanoparticles, *Appl. Mater. Today* 26 (2022) 101340 – 1-63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmt.2021.101340>.
- [14] Z.Wei, N.A.Liedienov, Q.Li, A.V.Pashchenko, W.Xu, V.A.Turchenko, M.Yuan, I.V.Fesychand, G.G.Levchenko, Influence of post-annealing, defect chemistry and high pressure on the magnetocaloric effect of non-stoichiometric $\text{La}_{0.8}\text{K}_{0.2}\text{Mn}_{1+x}\text{O}_3$ compounds. *Ceram. Int.* 47(17) (2021) 24553 – 24563. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2021.05.174>.
- [15] G.Suchanek, N.Kalanda, E.Artsiukh, M.Yarmolich, N.A.Sobolev, Tunneling conduction mechanisms in strontium ferromolybdate ceramics with strontium molybdate dielectric intergrain barriers, *J. Alloys Comp.* 860 (2021) 158526. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2020.158526>.
- [16] M.E.Matsnev, V.S.Rusakov, *SpectrRelax: An application for Mössbauer spectra modeling and fitting*, AIP Conference Proceedings (Vol. 1489, No. 1, pp. 178-185). American Institute of Physics, 2012
- [17] J.Söderlund, L.B.Kiss, G.A.Niklasson, C.G.Granqvist, Lognormal size distributions in particle growth processes without coagulation, *Physical review letters* 80 (1998) 2386 - 2388. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.80.2386>.
- [18] M.Yarmolich, N.Kalanda, S.Demyanov, Ju.Fedotova, V.Bayev, N.Sobolev, Charge ordering and magnetic properties in nanosized $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6.8}$ powders, *Phys. Status Solidi B.253* (2016) 2160–2166. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pssb.201600527>.
- [19] J.L.Dormann, L.Bessais, D.Fiorani, A dynamic study of small interacting particles: superparamagnetic model and spin-glass laws. *Journal of Physics C: Solid State Physics* 21 (1988) 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0022-3719/21/10/019>.
- [20] S.H.Kilcoyne, R.Cywinski, Ferritin: a model superparamagnet. *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials*, 140 (1995) 1466-1467. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-8853\(94\)00626-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-8853(94)00626-1)
- [21] C.P.Bean, J.D.Livingstone, Superparamagnetism, *J. Appl. Phys.* 30 (1959) 120S–129S. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2185850>
- [22] Yu.A.Koksharov, Magnetism of nanoparticles: effects of size, shape and interactions, in: S.P.Gubin (Ed.), *Magnetic Nanoparticles*, WILEY-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co., Weinheim, 2009, pp. 197 - 254
- [23] M.Gich, A.Roig, C.Frontera, E.Molins, J.Sort, M.Popovici, G.Chouteau, D.Martín y Marero, J. Nogues. Large coercivity and low-temperature magnetic reorientation in $\epsilon\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles, *Journal of Applied Physics* 98 (2005) 044307. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1997297>.
- [24] J.M.D.Coey, D.Khalafalla, Superparamagnetic $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$, *Physica status solidi (a)* 11 (1972) 229-241. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pssa.2210110125>.
- [25] S.P.Gubin, Yu.A.Koksharov, G.B.Khomutov, G.Yu.Yurkov, Magnetic nanoparticles: preparation, structure and properties, *Russian Chemical Reviews* 74 (2005) 489. <https://doi.org/10.1070/RC2005v074n06ABEH000897>.
- [26] R.Das, U.Chaudhuri, A.Chanda, R.Mahendiran, Broadband electron spin resonance study in a $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_6$ double perovskite, *ACS Omega* 5 (2020) 17611-17616. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.0c02070>.
- [27] R.Grössinger, A critical examination of the law of approach to saturation. I. Fit procedure, *Physica Status Solidi (a)* 66 (1981) 665-674. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pssa.2210660231>.
- [28] Z.K.Heiba, M.B.Mohamed, Structural phase analysis, optical and magnetic properties of nano Mn-doped LiFe_3O_8 , *Applied Physics A* 124 (2018) 818. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00339-018-2241-x>

- [29] Z.Q.Jin, W.Tang, J.R.Zhang, H.X.Qin, Y.W.Du, Effective magnetic anisotropy of nanocrystalline Nd-Fe-Ti-N hard magnetic alloys. *The European Physical Journal B* 3 (1998) 41-44. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s100510050282>
- [30] R.Das, U.Chaudhuri, R.Mahendiran, Microwave magnetoresistance and microwave absorption in $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_6$, *ACS Applied Electronic Materials* 3 (2021) 3072-3078. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaelm.1c00304>
- [31] T.Nosach, G.Mullady, N.Leifer, V.Adyam, Q.Li, S.Greenbaum, Y.Ren, Angular dependence of spin-wave resonance and relaxation in half-metallic $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_6$ films, *Journal of Applied Physics* 103 (2008) 07E311. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2837030>.
- [32] F.J.Dyson, Thermodynamic behavior of an ideal ferromagnet, *Physical Review*, 102 (1956) 1230. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRev.102.1230>
- [33] C.Kittel, *Introduction to Solid State Physics*, fourth ed., New York, Wiley, 1971.
- [34] G.Huo, X.Ren, L.Qian, N.Zhang, S.Liu, X.Yan, The disorder is induced by S doping at O-sites in double perovskite $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_6$ compound, *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials* 343 (2013) 119–125. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jmmm.2013.04.086>.
- [35] S.M.Bhagat, M.L.Spano, K.V.Rao, Temperature dependence of the magnetization in amorphous alloys, *Journal of Applied Physics*, 50 (1979) 1580-1582. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.327262>.
- [36] S.E.Lofland, T.Scabarozzi, Y.Moritomo, S.Xu, Magnetism of the double perovskite $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_6$, *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials*, 260 (2003)181-183. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-8853\(02\)01318-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-8853(02)01318-5).
- [37] Y.Moritomo, Sh.Xu, T.Akimoto, A. Machida, N. Hamada, K.Ohoyama, E. Nishibori, M. Takata, M. Sakata, Electron doping effects in conducting $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_6$, *Physical Review B* 62 (2000) 14224. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.62.14224>.
- [38] T.Yasuhide, T.Okuda, Y.Okimoto, R.Kumai, K-I.Kobayashi, Y.Tokura, Magnetic and electronic properties of a single crystal of ordered double perovskite $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_6$, *Physical Review B* 61 (2000) 422, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.61.422>.
- [39] M.Wójcik, E.Jędryka, S.Nadolski, J.Navarro, J.Fontcuberta, Mo–Fe antisite defects in $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_6$ studied by NMR, *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials*, 272 (2004) 1834-1835. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmmm.2003.12.822>.
- [40] A.P.Guimarães, Introduction to magnetotransport, in: *Principles of Nanomagnetism*, Springer, Berlin-Heidelberg, 2009, pp. 127-148. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-01482-6_5
- [41] F. Heider, W. Williams, Note on temperature dependence of exchange constant in magnetite, *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 15 (1988) 184-187. <https://doi.org/10.1029/GL015i002p00184>.
- [42] T.Suominen, J.Raittila, T.Salminen, K.Schlesier, J.Linden, P.Paturi, Magnetic properties of fine SFMO particles: Superparamagnetism. *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials*, 309 (2007) 278-284. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmmm.2006.07.016>.

Figure captions:

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of the $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ microstructure synthesized under combined annealing modes and quenched at room temperature. Inset: AFM image of the $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ powder grains

Fig. 2. Size distribution of the volume fraction of the $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ particles after the ultrasonic dispersion: DLS analysis (black) and its approximation by the log-normalized function $f(d)$ (red). Inset: AFM image of the $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ powder grains after dispersion

Fig. 3. Temperature dependence of the magnetization of the $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ nanopowder synthesized under combined conditions in a magnetic field of 0.01 T

Fig. 4. Temperature evolution of the Mössbauer spectra. The interpretation of the spectra is shown by a solid line, the corresponding components - in color (sextet S – 1 - gray, sextet S – 2 - red, sextet S – 3 - blue, sextet S – 4 - green, doublet - dark gray)

Fig. 5. Approximation of the experimental data for the field dependence of the magnetization of the $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ nanopowder: (a) using eq. 2; (b) using eq. 5

Fig. 6. Field dependence of the $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ nanopowder magnetization at 25 K: (1) total value; (2) calculated ferrimagnetic component; (3) calculated superparamagnetic component

Fig. 7. Temperature dependence of the magnetization of the $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ nanopowder synthesized under combined conditions, measured in an external magnetic field of 0.01 T: (a) experimental data; (b - d) approximations calculated using eqs. 10 – 12, respectively

Fig. 8. Temperature dependences of the $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ nanopowder magnetization: (1) total value of the magnetization measured in the FC mode in a field of 0.01 T; (2) calculated ferrimagnetic component; (3) calculated superparamagnetic component

Tables:

Table 1. Fitting coefficients and calculated magnetic characteristics of the nanosized $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ grains in a ferrimagnetic state, obtained by approximating the field dependence of the magnetization using eq. 2

M_{fH0} , A·m ² /kg	a , A/m	b , A ² /m ²	M_{fH1} , A/m	H_{fa} , A/m	K_f , J/m ³	R^2
34.67	7.7×10^5	1.85×10^9	0.00283	1.67×10^5	1.99×10^4	0.9776

Table 2. Calculated magnetic characteristics of the nanosized $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_{6-\delta}$ grains obtained by approximating the experimental data of the field dependence of the magnetization using eq. 5 ($R^2 = 0.9991$)

Superparamagnetic phase			Ferrimagnetic phase	
H_{sa} , A/m	K_s , J/m ³	n_{sp} , cm ⁻³	H_{fa} , A/m	K_f , J/m ³
6.12×10^7	1.64×10^6	2.4×10^{20}	1.45×10^5	1.61×10^4

Figures

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

Fig. 7

Fig. 8